

SOCIOLOGY OF LAW, SUBJECT, EDUCATIONAL CONTENT AND IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

The subject of this paper is a question of general sociology because sociology is one of the most complex sciences, both in comparison with natural sciences and in comparison with social sciences. Bearing in mind the fact that each science is determined primarily by its subject matter, and then by its method, the conclusion is drawn that most of the sciences are closely intertwined with either an object, either by methods that are very difficult to separate. Further, this paper clarifies the issue of the subject of the theory of state and law. The theory of state and law appears as a unique discipline only in the late twentieth century, which has the task of studying the state and law. In the end, the subject and methods of sociology of law are studied as a special scientific discipline. Sociology of Law is one of the youngest social sciences. There are different opinions and attitudes regarding the determination of sociology of law as a special scientific discipline, as well as disagreement whether it belongs to legal, or sociological sciences. The method of any scientific discipline depends directly on the subject of its study, which certainly applies to the sociology of law.

Keywords: sociology, law, subject, methods, scientific disciplines.

1. Introduction

The notion of sociology of law causes many doubts and debates in science. It is difficult to find two identical opinions about the concept and importance of this discipline. The frenzy of the discussion, both in terms of the concept and the place of this science, is in no way surprising. Namely, sociology of law represents an extremely young scientific discipline. Recall, Ogist Cont only in 1839 distinguishes general socialism as a special science. Sociology of the law is even younger, it is, as it is often said, a child of the 20th century. The frenzy of the debate on this issue, it seems, is still not bleeding. Although Western democracies have developed in the developed countries and there is not much debate about some basic issues regarding the sociology of law as a special doctrine, this seems to be not the case with the countries of central and eastern Europe that are in the process of transition (unfortunately, it seems this is more relevant to us than to other countries in the environment). This difference in opinion is so great that it goes on to exaggerate the significance of the sociology of law to the detriment of others, otherwise close to her science (and above all, we bear in mind, first of all, the theory and philosophy of law), or, to the complete negation, not only of its significance, but also existence. We do not want to go into more detail in these differences (especially considering that practice constantly shows that the existence of sociology of law as a special science is not only possible but also necessary), we will try to define something more closely the notion of sociology of law. If one accepts the view that "every science is determined primarily by its object and then by its method" (Lukic, 1995d, 16), it is clear that most of the basic disciplines are closely intertwined (either by subject or by methods that are very difficult to separate) . This is especially true for the sociology of law that arises in the midst of general sociology and law. (Maksimovic, 2000, 175) Without going into the question of belonging sociology of law to legal or sociological doctrines, but taking into account the close interaction with her, we consider it necessary determine its notion, that is, its special object and method. It seems necessary that, precisely because of this interwovenness, as a preliminary question, a subject is defined as general sociology and other cognitive disciplines related to close sociology of law, with particular reference to both theory and the philosophy of law.

2. Sociology and relations with other sciences

Sociology is one of the most complex sciences, both in comparison with natural sciences and in comparison with social sciences. This complexity stems from both the social reality it is studying and the methods it serves to study this reality. For these reasons, the definition of sociology is not easy. There are numerous attempts, among which, unfortunately, those who for many reasons do not satisfy. It seems that those approaches can not be accepted, which, considering that determining the subject of sociology is not an essential issue, avoid specifying the subject of this science in a clear and precise manner. These attempts are mostly reduced to the definition of sociology as the science of the most important characteristics of society (as does Dz. S. Mil.) (Gurvic, 1966, 12).

Such attitudes actually seek to establish that sociology is merely the sum of all social sciences, nothing else to a common name for all specific social sciences. We think that denial of autonomy

and peculiarity, as sociology of one, and special social sciences, on the other hand, can in no way contribute to the precise determination of this scientific discipline, but only blur the problem. In seeking to achieve this goal, that is, to clearly define the subject of sociology, many theorists based their definitions of sociology on formalistic settings.

Despite the great importance of the formalistic approach to sociology, one can not overlook the fact that advocates of formalism unilaterally observe the subject of sociology. Namely, from the conceptual definition of this scientific discipline, they expel all the cultural activity in one society, as well as the activities of social groups (in that we mean religion, morality, art and other phenomena) by reducing its object to a mere form, shape (of course, assuming different things under him). As a reaction to the formalistic understanding of sociology, the so-called cultural approach appears. Their perception of sociology is diametrically opposed to formalism, and it falls to the extreme, just on the opposite side. The subject of sociology is not sufficiently precisely defined, and it is mixed and lost in terms of culture and civilization. According to advocates of this direction, the subject of sociology is reduced to studying various types of groups and society, that is, studying their culture and civilization. It seems that none of these definitions fully satisfies it since it unilaterally determines the subject of sociology. Gurvich argues that none of the great founders of sociology (which includes Sen Simon, Prudon, Konta, Marx and Spenser) have no definition of sociology that would be adequate to their real ideas, but that they can only be found only indications of the subject of sociology, but a clearly defined subject of this science. (Gurvic, 1966, 16) It seems that Gurvich seems to be perhaps the most complete definition of the subject of sociology by determining its field and its method. Thus, he determines sociology as "qualitative and discontinuous, on a dialectically based typology of structural, structured and structured total social phenomena, which she studies in the same way, in all depth layers, on all scales, and in all sectors, with the tendency to follow their movement patterns, destructing, restructuring and decaying the structure, and to explain them in cooperation with history "(Gurvic, 1966, 36) or something shorter and clearer, as" a science that studies total social phenomena in the totality of their forms and their movements, classifying them into dialectically expressed micro-social grouping and global types that are continuously emerging and disappearing. " (Gurvic, 1966, 36)

Prior to conferring all social sciences on special and general, as well as unifying and general, our prominent scholar, Radomir Lukic, defines sociology as a general and general science. (Lukic, 1995d, 40) In his opinion, sociology includes two subjects that, in addition to their generality, are not identical. This sociology first studies what is common to all spiritual phenomena, and in the second place it studies human society as a whole of all phenomena in society, the laws of their connection and the development of society as a whole. Thus, in addition to studying the general and common in all social phenomena, sociology studies the connection of these phenomena as a whole and the development of that whole. (Lukic, 1995d, 41). From this it follows that sociology studies how the static of society (embodied in the notion of society and composition represented by social phenomena), as well as the dynamics of society (embodied in relations and interaction in society itself, as well as in relations between society and out-of-wedlock phenomena). We are skeptical that we consider that these two conceptual conclusions of sociology, although in some segments different, define the subject of sociology most precisely, and that therefore they are the most acceptable.

3. Sociology and law relations

Although the theory of law, understood in the broadest sense, as the disciplinary discipline that has the subject of studying law and state, is considered one of the oldest social sciences, the matter that today belongs to the theory of state and law has not always been the subject of special scientific discipline. As a unique, independent scientific discipline, which has the task of studying the state and law, that is, to provide abstract and general knowledge about them, it occurs only at the end of the nineteenth century. Relatively independent development of the doctrine of the state and law to the nineteenth century has led to numerous approaches to these phenomena. In the twentieth century, the issue of the theory of state theory and law as an independent science is especially important. In particular, the question of her relationship with related science is especially acute, and especially with the philosophy of the law within which they develop, in addition to the new system of philosophy of law and the natural-legal and rationalist philosophy of law. Radomir Lukic emphasizes the specialty of the theory of state and law, that is, the specialty of general teaching about the state and law. (Lukic, 1995f, 47) In his opinion, it takes an independent place, both in relation to positive-legal and in relation to historical-legal sciences. The theory of state and law is an abstract and legal science, that is, a scientific discipline that gives general, fundamental knowledge of the state and law. (Lukic, 1995f, 18) Generally speaking, the subject of the theory of state and law is the state and law as objectively present in the world. As theory of state and law is abstract law, it does not, according to Lukic, examine any particular state and law, but "only studies those qualities and relationships that are general, and thus relevant to the state and the law." (Lukic, 1995f, 50) Accordingly, Lukic determines the subject of this discipline as "general qualities and general relations of the state and the right" (Lukic, 1995f, 50) expressed in terms of general concepts and laws on state and law. (Lukic, 1995f, 50). In this connection, it is particularly interesting to distinguish basic and general concepts, that is, which of them (or perhaps both) constitute the content of the theory of the state and the right, and thus determine her subject. This distinction begins at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, the beginning of the use of the sociological method in the theory of state and law. Since the legal method examines the law and the state as a purely legal phenomenon, its application leads to the creation of general concepts that are purely legal and obtained by generalizing from special legal sciences. Since the legal method does not include what the state and the right associate with other phenomena, it can not be solely by its application to determine the highest, basic, necessary concepts without which no state can be imagined and no right. (Lukic, 1995f, 54) Lukic believes that this distinction is useful because it indicates which links are more important and important than others. In any case, even though it is accepted that the basic concepts do not exist, the theory of state and law does not lose the character of independent science because it "only studies what is common in all concrete manifestations of the state and the law." (Lukic, 1995f, 55)

Hans Kelzen, one of the main representatives of normative theories of law, points out the dogmatic and normative character of jurisprudence as the unprincipled assumption of any legal science. (Kelzen, 2001, 8) According to him, in order to construct the basic legal concepts it is necessary to completely eliminate the explicit and complete acceptance of the normative point of view. (Kelzen, 2001, 8) Kelzen sees the theory of law (even the state) as a pure theory, or a theory of positive law. According to his opinion, the sociological approach wants to be causative by the scientific method to be governed by the law as part of the natural reality, while the theory of natural law ignores the basis of the relationship that is given only in positive law. Such

perceptions do not ensure the independence of rights as a matter of scientific knowledge. (Kelzen, 2001, 13) Kelzen points out that the fundamental problem of the theory of the state and the right relationship is between the law and the state. Rejecting the metaphorical notion of the state, Kelzen points to its homogeneous nature, or to the unity of the state and the legal order. (Kelzen, 2001, 24). The normative character of the theory of law is, according to Kelzen, two, both negative and positive. It is negative in the fact that it is not an explicit discipline (it does not reflect the actual events that belong to the state of being), and it is positively expressed in the fact that for its subject there are norms from which specific legal terms are derived. (Kelzen, 2001, 34) The theory of law therefore has a task to find out what is and what is right, and in no way try to determine what it should be. (Kelzen, 1998, 11) The theory of state and rights can be defined as "an abstract, basic and general general legal science dealing with the state and law as such". (Mitrovic, 1992, 15) Although basically true - such a definition of this scientific discipline is not the most complete and most precise. Namely, if in terms of the state, as one of the subjects of the study of the theory of the state and the law, and there is not much slow (despite the different understanding of the state) - this is not the case with law. The fact is that we should first determine what is rightly implied, bearing in mind the precise determination of the subject of this science. Putting aside the differences that exist among numerous theorists in the understanding of rights (let us remind that Kant once claimed that lawyers do not yet know what is right, even though they are so much debated about it), we consider that under the right in the above definition only positive law, that is, law which is sanctioned by the state (so-called state, or even better - state law).

4. Issues of Philosophy of law

The philosophy of law is the oldest form of observation and the realization of law. The early beginnings of philosophical thoughts on law should be sought in the political doctrines of the Old East, and a special excitement of the philosophy of law (though still within the framework of general philosophy) is experienced in the rich thought of ancient Greece. (Mitrovic, 1992, 7). Without wishing to separately go into the distinction between the philosophy of the law of related disciplines (in this case we especially refer to the theory of law), we recall the possible relations of the philosophy of law with related disciplines, which was very precisely determined by R. Tokarcik, professor at the Lublin Law School. (Podgorac, 1998, 10)

There is more understanding of what under the philosophy of law should be implied. We think that they are not good approaches that negate the existence of the philosophy of law, or are determined so that they are practically reduced to the theory of law (Karkunov, Radbruh, Bobio). The contrary views of these are numerous philosophical and legal thinkers. Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel takes a particularly prominent place. As an object of the philosophy of law, which he otherwise calls the philosophical legal science, he defines the idea of law and the concept of law. (Hegel, 1989, 20) By distinguishing the notion and its existence, Hegel claims that these two phenomena, although separated, are simultaneously inextricably linked as souls and bodies. (Hegel, 1989, 21) The notion of rights to its origin comes from the law of law; his deduction, according to Hegel, is assumed and as a given must be accepted. The unity of the notion of law and its existence constitutes an idea of the freedom which represents to Hegel. The philosophy of law deals with the intellectual law that, according to Hegel, can be distinguished from its external appearance (positive law), which can be silly (but that it is no less true). The

philosophy of law, according to Hegel, is the task of developing the idea of rights from the notion of law. Leon Petrazicki, a prominent Polish theoretician of law, takes a prominent place in philosophical legal thought. Leon Petrazicki dealt with the philosophy of law at the same time developing his experiential-psychological theory of law, and laying the foundations of the law of law policy practically in all periods of his creative work. (Podgorac, 1999, 158) Leon Petrazicki very broadly sets the foundations of the philosophy of law. In his work "The Line of the Law of Philosophy" Petrazicki says that "under the philosophy of law we mean learning about law, both from a theoretical point of view and from a political point of view, in other words, a science that contains in itself 1) theory, 2) a policy of law." (Podgorac, 1999, 159). The philosophy of law is viewed by Petrazzi as a unifying, computational science, that is, the philosophy of law is the sum of the highest theory and the highest teleology (politics) of law. (Philosophia iuris = summa theoria + summa teleologia (politics) iuris). (Podgorac, 1999, 161)

R. Lukic's philosophical legal thought also deserves attention. Lukic under the subject of the philosophy of law implies the supreme right of the law. The right in his opinion has two forms: the first is an experiential (positive) right, and the dear is a supersensible (objective) right. From this it follows that the philosophy of law is studied by: 1) general insight; 2) the oversight of positive law; 3) special legal supervision (objective law). (Lukic, 1995e, 320) Lukic believes that the philosophy of law encompasses the basic branches of philosophy by specifying them and applying it to the law. According to this, the philosophy of law, according to Lukic, is divided into ontology, axiology and gnoseology of law. (Lukic, 1995e, 326) Ontology of law reveals the right for itself and its supersensible elements. It also reveals ontological connections of law with other phenomena in the world and the world as a whole. (Lukic, 1995e, 335) The axiology of law, such as general aksiology, introduces learning about values (to the extent that these are related to law). It determines the legal values (their ontological essence) and the possibility of their realization, as well as their relations with one another and with other values. In addition, axiology determines the value of the right itself as a special phenomenon. (Lukic, 1995e, 484) The gnoseology of law deals with the possibility of knowing the rights as a special phenomenon. By exercising the right to a positive and objective, Lukic believes that the gnoseology of the law is divided into these two types.

Stevan K. Vracar also examines in detail the concept of the philosophy of law. Highlighting the number of views on the character of the philosophy of law, he points in particular to the significance of the questionnaire devoted to the issue of determining the notion of the philosophy of law, initiated at the beginning of the sixties in the distinguished annual "Archives for the Philosophy of Law". (Vracar, 1995, 30) Participation in this survey was taken by thirty prominent philosophers and lawyers trying to define this discipline. All these different views Vracar groups into those that emphasize the philosophical character of the philosophy of law, then to those that specifically emphasize the methodological character of this scientific discipline, as well as those that give special attention to the complexity and complexity of the concept of the philosophy of law. Recalling the first group of perceptions, Vracar believes that they do not give a precise definition of the philosophy of law because they represent a kind of deductive performance of the character of the philosophy of law from the character of general philosophy, and there is also no subject definition of the philosophy of law. (Vracar, 1995, 35) As regards those who emphasize primarily the methodological character of the philosophy of law, Vracar distinguishes three groups of perceptions. Thus, the first group of perceptions emphasizes the methodological importance of determining subjects of philosophy and legal science. (Vracar, 1995, 35). Common to these ideas is that the philosophy of law is represented

as a methodology of legal science. Vracar believes that the problem of the method fully observed can not be reduced to the philosophy of law because it goes beyond its frameworks. (Vracar, 1995, 37). Another group of perceptions, as he claims, far more emphasizes the legal science, which is the predominant area in which the function of the philosophy of law as a methodology is realized. Accordingly, the philosophy of law "does not draw its methodological character only from philosophy, but also from legal science." (Vracar, 1995, 38). The third group of ideas explicitly emphasizes the methodological character of this scientific discipline. Vracar is of the opinion that such perceptions can be considered founded on this fence so that the philosophy of law and legal methodology can not literally be equated if one considers that the objects and the role they belong to are different. In his opinion, the most favorable definition of the true character of the philosophy of law gives those notions indicating the complexity of this discipline, i.e. on the complexity and complexity of both the object and the method. Vracar himself considers that it can not be said that the subject of the philosophy of law is the right, because it constitutes an unsubstantiated claim, since it must first be determined what is meant by the law. He advocates the view of the necessity of philosophical comprehension and the consideration of exclusively existing law. (Vracar, 1995, 49). The philosophy of law should also include a set of rights, i.e. the overall legal reality and certain legal phenomena. This discerning discipline, as he already points out, is the most widely known knowledge that provides "the most important qualities and connections that the right shows by finding themselves in the world of infinitely varied and objectively existing phenomena." (Vracar, 1995, 50) In addition to all this, Vracar emphasizes that the philosophy of rights must not neglect the fact that the right is connected with the state, and in fact this discipline could also turn into a philosophy of law and state.

Having in mind all the above stated, we consider that the most complete definition of the subject of the philosophy of law is what it considers to be the study of an essential, natural, rational, or ideal genuine right. In other words, the philosophy of law deals with the possibility of knowing the rights, the procedures that come to this knowledge, by determining the rights of the right arising from the nature of man and interpersonal relations and the right as value, with which other values are related. (Podgorac, 1999, 40)

5. Difficulties in determining subjects of sociology of law

Difficulties in determining subjects of sociology of law arise for several reasons. First of all, this scientific discipline is one of the youngest social sciences. Furthermore, it is on the very borders of sociology and legal science, and there are also attitudes that determine this science as a common denominator of these disciplines. Moreover, those who regard the sociology of law as a special scientific discipline often can not agree on whether it belongs to legal, or sociological doctrines. Although we do not consider the question of belonging to the sociology of law as any of the disciplines is an essential issue, it seems to us that it is important to note that this distinction in thought is the result of a different interpretation of the basic issues of sociology and law. Those who consider this discipline as exclusively legal, consider that sociology of law forms an integral part of the theory of law and the legal phenomenon is observed according to their function of preserving a certain order. On the other hand, advocates of the attitude about the sociological character of this science, think that the sociology of rights views reality as far as it is related to legal factors. While paying first-most attention to the consequences of the application

of positive law, others put the emphasis on studying the specificity of social phenomena to which influence exercises the law and spread it (thus not only positive law). (Maksimovic, 2000, 176) Leaving aside this dispute, it should be pointed out that there are a whole range of different views of this subject's subject.

Of particular interest is the opinion of Jana Carbonia . According to Carbonia, the notion of legal sociology sometimes has a somewhat broader meaning than the concept of sociology of law. First, it would include all phenomena that the right has a greater or lesser influence, therefore, those phenomena that the law may cause, or may arise as their consequence, while the other would only encompass what constitutes just the right (rules and institutions). (Carbini, 1992, 6) By identifying the widest possible field of study, Carbonia considers that one or the other meaning should be used without distinction. (Carbini, 1992, 6) Determining the sociology of law as a branch of general sociology, Carbonia claims that its subject matter is legal. Namely, in his opinion, the claim that the law is the subject of the sociology of law can not satisfy it, because it is the subject of the so-called " dogmatic law, or theory of law. For Carbonia, the subject of both sciences is the same, only the angle of observation is different. (Carbini, 1992, 126). While the law studied by the so- dogmatic law, represents a "coherent and monolithic entity" (Carbini, 1992, 126), until sociology of law breaks down this unique entity into "countless legal atoms of random combinations" (Carbini, 1992, 126). in countless legal phenomena. Although, according to Carbonia, general sociology does not differentiate the concepts of social facts and social phenomena, the sociology of the law of the sea, in order to make a clearer definition of its case, distinguish between legal facts and legal phenomena, since these first have a precise and different meaning in dogmatic law. (Carbini, 1992, 126). All the legal phenomena of Carbonia are classified into four basic groups, that is, we can speak of four classifications of legal phenomena. (Carbini, 1992, 127) Thus, the first classification includes primary and secondary legal phenomena. Primary are the legal phenomena which are the most general, that is, those from which all other legal phenomena arise (here the Carbonia includes the legal text, the pronouncement of the judgment, and the like). The very content of such perceived primary phenomena, in his opinion, is a secondary legal phenomenon. Since it is a causal relationship, Carbonia claims that "the primary phenomenon is the generator of secondary phenomena." (Carbini, 1992, 128) The common trait of primary phenomena is that they all appear as authority or authority.

Accordingly, all others are secondary, i.e. derived legal phenomena. The second classification includes phenomena with power and emergence under authority, and Carbonia considers that it can be viewed as a subclause of primary legal phenomena. (Carbini, 1992, 131) The former would include those legal phenomena whose essence is power and which have the most general character (here Carbonia includes the appearance of authorities threatened by the ruler, subjective law, etc.). (Carbini, 1992, 131) The occurrences under the rule include the first order of behavior, states of consciousness and have somewhat subjective character. Here Carbonia includes those phenomena that provide an answer, that is, a reaction to the emergence of authority (on order, judgment, etc.), as well as some psychological phenomena such as knowledge and perceptions of law, legal awareness, and legal reasoning. In his third classification, he includes the appearance of the institution and the occurrence of cases. Occurrences are a derivative of the appearance of institutions and represents its application (marriage as an institution and marriage as a case in life). "The phenomena of the institutions are distinguished by their historical individuality, while the cases are numerous". (Carbini, 1992,

134) Occurrence cases can accordingly be studied in two basic ways, both individual and collective phenomena. Since, as he claims, there are cases in their nature of the appearance of relations, that is, the emergence of relations, they can be viewed from the point of view of existing interactions, which, in his opinion, can be troikas, and include, cooperation, match and conflict. (Carbini, 1992, 137) The fourth classification relates to controversial and uncontested legal phenomena. The first legal phenomena arise in one or the occasion of a process, that is, of a dispute, while in the other group of legal phenomena we consider all other legal phenomena. Carbonium considers that "the dispute deforms the reality of law and that law is infinitely broader than dispute" (Carbinus, 1992, 139) and favors uncontested legal phenomena.

The contribution of Jorge Gurvich, which defines the sociology of law as "the part of the sociology of the human spirit that studies the full social reality of the law, starting from its tangible and externally visible manifestations in effective behaviors and continuing with its material basis" is exceptionally significant. (Gurvich , 1997, 68). The sociology of law deals with the study of legal symbolic forms set in advance (organized law, sanctions), as well as the study of legal symbols, legal values and collective beliefs, which are manifested in, as Gurvich says, the positivity of the whole rights. (Gurvich , 1997, 68). As he claims, three are the basic problems of the sociology of law, that is, the three basic directions of studying her subject. In the first case, it is a problem of the sociology of the right that refers to "manifestations of rights as functions of the form of sociality and level of social reality". (Gurvich , 1997, 139). The study of the manifestation of rights as a function of real collective units Gurvich is considered to be a problem of differential sociology of law, while the study of regularity as a factor of the application, development and decay of rights in particular types of society falls within the problems of genetic sociology. (Gurvich, 1997, 139). This division of the subject of sociology of law, in his opinion, arises from the fact that the society is composed of different groups, and that each individual group consists of several forms of sociality. The systematic sociology of law (that is, the microsociology of law as Gurvich proposes) represents the relationship between social reality and the type of law, where it is necessary to distinguish between categories of rights, as well as rights and rights systems. Rights frameworks can only arise in collective units and represent an expression of the balance between different types of rights. The law systems, however, arise in comprehensive societies and combine different rights frameworks. According to Gurvich, the microsociology of law must, on the one hand, "examine the types of rights as functions of different forms of sociality" (Gurvich , 1997, 189), and, on the other hand, "studies the types of law as functions of the depth layers that can be found in every form of sociality ". (Gurvich, 1997, 189). As microsociology of law must distinguish as many types of rights as there is a form of sociality, Gurvich distinguishes the existence of three basic groups of types of rights. (Gurvich, 1997, 196) In the first group, Gurvich includes social law and individual (or inter-individual) law. The first is the right to objective integration and is based on trust, while the other is based on distrust, because unlike social separation and limiting interests of the subjects.

The second group, as he points out, encompasses the social law of the masses and the right of the narrower and broader communities. Gurvich believes that the social law of the masses is the least intense in terms of value, and the most intensive for violence, since the masses are the weakest in the merger, and the strongest in pressure. (Gurvich, 1997, 198). This right is therefore characterized by the exclusion of the so-called. objective law (the rights of collectivity), with reference to regulations, and almost complete negation of subjective rights. Contrary to this, there is a much greater balance between objective social rights and subjective social rights in

community law. The interindividual right of separation, approximation and the right of mixed structure make the third group of types of rights. The first right arises in a conflict, that is, in a struggle, characterized by the fact of dominance and differentiation of rights, without any formation of obligations. (Gurvich, 1997, 202) The largest number of relationships, on the basis of which an interindividual right of convergence arises, has a mostly passive character (relations based on gifts, one-sided concessions, and the like). The individual law born in this way, in his opinion, has the most peaceful character. The individual law of the mixed structure is the most widespread and its classic manifestation is contract law (there are also transactions, loans, etc.). In this law, the equilibrium between rights and obligations arises. Unlike systematic sociology of law, the differential sociology of law, as Gurvich already points out, studies the macrophysical aspect of legal reality. (Gurvich, 1997, 213) Consequently, it is no longer possible to speak of species, but of frameworks and systems of law. Consequently, the differential sociology of law examines both the legal typology of specific groups and the legal typology of all-encompassing societies. Thus, in the first case, Gurvich distinguishes: 1) special and inclusive groups, 2) temporary and permanent groups, 3) groups based on function, 4) disruptive and uniting groups, 5) unorganized and organized groups, 6) groups with conditional and with unconditional coercion and 7) unitary, federal and confederal groups. (Gurvich, 1997, 221) Considering that "each group in which active sociability prevails and in which a certain positive value is attained as a normative fact" (Gurvich, 1997, 222) each of these groups creates legal frameworks. Depending on the group that creates them, Gurvich distinguishes the following framework of rights: 1) the frameworks of political, economic and mystical-ecstatic law; 2) unitary, federal and confederal rights frameworks; 3) torn and unifying frameworks of rights; 4) national and international rights frameworks.

In the case of legal typology of comprehensive societies, we are talking about legal systems, that is, about systems of law. Pointing out the great difficulties in establishing a unified and generally accepted typology and classification, Gurvich considers that seven legal types of comprehensive societies can be distinguished: "1) legal systems of polysegmental societies that have a magical religious basis, 2) legal systems of societies that are homogeneous 3) the legal systems of societies that have gained homogeneity through the domination of the domestic political group, 4) the legal systems of feudal societies based on the legal power of the church, 5) the legal systems of societies united through the superiority of the city or the empire;) legal systems of united nations through the superiority of the territorial state and the autonomy of individual will; 7) legal systems of contemporary societies in which groups are formed on the basis of economic activity and the territorial state struggles for a new legal balance. (Gurvich, 1997, 237) Genetic sociology of law includes the third direction of the study of sociology of law. This sociology of law, according to Gurvich's opinion, should reject the notion that the continuing development of legal institutions can be found even in a primitive society, and, in passing, there are two basic directions characteristic of its study. Genetic sociology of law must first of all examine the regularities that represent the tendencies of change within each particular type of legal system, as well as to study factors that are characteristic of these regularities of change. (Gurvich, 1997, 261)

We are inclined to consider that a particularly significant contribution to the close determination of the subject of sociology of law is given by Adam Podgurecki, a prominent Polish sociologist of law. According to germ, this scientific discipline tries to realize social reality to the extent that this reality is connected with the legal factor. She, therefore, studies the determining of social reality by law, as well as the determination of the right to social reality. Sociology of law studies

the right in its functioning, and above all it could, with its recommendations, lead to rational and efficient transformations in society. In order to achieve this, its conclusions must be such as to enable their practical application as easy as possible. (Podgorac, 2000, 226)

Particularly interesting is Podgureck's opinion on the relationship between the sociology of law and the law of law politics. This sociologist of law considers that the policy of law is equivalent to the sociology of law, that is, - believes that the law of law is an applied sociology of law. From this it follows practically that the sociology of law determines the causal links that relate to the functioning of the law, while the policy of the law deals with the way in which such relationships are established to achieve their goals. Ultimately, and sociology of law, such as law politics, starting from the question of *de lege lata* speaks of *de lege ferenda*. Both sciences should represent and represent the means of reforming positive law. Podgurica gives, as it seems, the most complete definition of the subject of sociology of law. Thus, according to him, "the sociology of the law deals with the registration, formulation and verification of all those interdependencies, which in their composition have one legal and one factor of some other kind." (Maksimovic, 2000, 177)

Lukic also recognizes the need for the existence of sociology of law. Defining the law as an undoubtedly social phenomenon that exists in a particular society among people and in their consciousness, Lukic clearly distinguishes the normative, spiritual, ideal side of the law that can not exist independently of that right that exists in the consciousness and behavior of people. By establishing the correlation of human behavior with law, he argues that society influences the creation of rights, just as the only law affects human behavior, that is, on society as a whole. Once created under the social influence, the law (or norm) created its effect on society, or on human behavior, regardless of whether it is still part of a positive legal order, or not. This right does not necessarily coincide with the positive, because it can exist when there is no positive right, as it may not exist when a positive right exists. This kind of sociological character of the law connects, ie. it causes other social processes associated with it (ie, taking a position according to law, creating negative or positive legal awareness, etc.). According to his views, the subject of sociology of law implies, on the one hand, the study of the influence that society has on the right (in particular its content) and its overall functioning, and on the other hand, the study of the influence of the right to society and its direction in one or in the other direction. In other words, the sociology of law studies the real right and the differences between it and the positive law, the origin of these differences, as well as four, according to Lukic, the main social and legal process in which it includes: 1) the social processes from which the social existence of the law consists, 2) the creation of rights, 3) the influence of the right to society, and 4) the influence of the society on the law. (Lukic, 1995c, 95-102) In his lecture, Professor Lukic dealt with the concept of sociology of law in detail. He believes that in determining the essence of sociology of law, the method may be even more important than the subject, since the subject of every science, including the sociology of law, is determined using its methods. (Lukic, 1991, 307) As the method of sociology of law, in addition to the positive one, includes the right that actually exists in society, it restricts the subject of sociology of law to a true fact. "(Lukic, 1991, 309) Here, in his opinion, According to this, sociology of rights includes the right spontaneously created by society, which is kept on the consciousness of people, regardless of the state organization, thus exceeding the limits of positive law in the society. (Lukic, 1991, 309) The right to be seen in this way has several aspects: it can be regarded as a product of society, and consequently, the subject

of sociology of law would be the becoming and development of rights. then it can also be said about the law of law as an object of sociology of law. From all that follows, it follows that, given that both of these aspects show the right to move, this subject of sociology of law can be called right (Lukic, 1991, 309) In addition to this, as Lukic claims, sociology of rights also includes a legal static, which examines the internal structure of the legal system by observing it in its rest. (Lukic, 1991, 310) Bearing in mind that the right, as he thinks, as an object of the sociology of law, has its ideal side, which to some extent goes beyond the scope of this scientific discipline, Lukic raises the question of the possibility of this scientific discipline to include this ideal element. In his view, sociology of law can include this ideal side only to the extent that this ideal side is in the being, that is, in consciousness (if that ideal is a fact). (Lukic, 1991, 315) This ideal moment of law can be seen in the case of law, while posture and the structure of law are mainly sociological problems.

Yugoslav Stankovic defines sociology of law as "nothing but a sociological theory and method applied to the examination of the phenomenon we call the law." (Stankovic, 2000, 238) Accordingly, the precise definition of a subject of sociology of law depends on what the term implies. The application of the sociological method, according to Stankovic's opinion, shows that the notion of rights seen from a sociological point of view is not identical to the notion of the rights observed by normative sciences. "Sociology of law is interested in the law as a social phenomenon, that is, the phenomenon that is realized in the real inevitably connected behavior of different subjects." (Stankovic, 2000, 238) In addition, Stankovic argues that sociology of law must study the creation, creation and functioning of rights under the influence of other phenomena in society. This impact of society on the law is generally realized in two ways. On the one hand, society influences the creation of rights, and on the other, society influences its application. As he already claims, the process of creating rights has two basic aspects. Sociology of law, in the first case, extends the influence of various social phenomena, frameworks and partial and global communities on the origin and characteristics of rights. In other words, "the sociology of law is interested in how the social facts, social processes are taken into the normative norms". (Stankovic, 2000, 241). In the second case, sociology of law examines the influence of social factors on the formal process of creation of rights by bodies that have such a right. (Stankovic, 2000, 241) Stankovic called this study a sociology of legislative activity and it aims to, based on the concrete material collected in concrete societies, that the response that influences the creation of rights in different societies. Sociology of law also has to determine the real social frameworks in which the law is applied, as well as the measure of its application, that is, it is not applied in concrete societies. Stankovic believes that the application issues should have two aspects. (Stankovic, 2000, 242) The first aspect includes the primary application of the law, ie the acceptance of rights by subjects to whom the legal order is addressed (citizens, various social organizations). Another aspect of this problem is the so-called. the secondary application of the law or the application of rights by the institutions created for its implementation (the court and other executive and administrative bodies). Stankovic believes that sociology of law must also study the influence of the right to society. This, first and foremost, involves determining which values represent the right and in whose interest it operates. Also, sociology of the right I am for the task of determining the real impact of the right as such on the changes in social relations, as well as to study and determine the efficiency of the law. (Stankovic, 2000, 245) As the last task of the sociology of law, Stankovic emphasizes the study and determination of the possible lawfulness of the development of the law which, according to

him, would be a synthesis of those results obtained by studying previous questions in concrete societies. (Stankovic, 2000, 246)

It should be noted that when we talk about the subject of sociology of law, we can distinguish two levels, that is, two kinds of sociology of law. The first level represents the theoretical sociology of law, that is, the one that studies the law as a social institution. The second level represents a practical sociology of law, that is discipline which would in fact be one of the forms of legal policy. (Maksimovic, 2000, 178). From the foregoing, that sociology of law has "the object of its study of the social conditionality of the rights and consequences of its action" (Maksimovic, 2000, 222), that is, its subject is reduced to the study of "three things: socio-conditionality of legal regulations, social psychological mechanism of their effect and their effectiveness ". (Maksimovic, 2000, 228)

6. Conclusion

It seems to us that everything has previously been shown to show the justified need for further and deeper engagement with sociology of law. There are many questions that still need to be answered. In addition to the general sociology of the law discussed here, there are, of course, special sociologies of law (sociology of criminal, family, constitutional law, etc.) that require detailed study. The difference, which is not usually done in our country, exists between legal sociology and sociology of law. The particular importance of sociology of law comes from the point of view of its practical application, that is, the significance of its attitudes regarding the creation, interpretation and application of the law. It provides lawyers with an objective description of the social reality of the rights in a given society, creating them conditions for working on a systematic forecasting of the future development of rights. Sociology of law bridles the differences that exist between a legislator, a law-abiding lawyer and a lawyer who is right in practice. That is why this scientific discipline, in the best possible way, helps to eliminate discrepancies between the prescribed and the actual, between the rights in books and life. In this, perhaps, her greatest significance and contribution are reflected.

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